

NFDI4Objects
Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Temporary Working Group (TWG)

Status quo of the material qualities of written artefacts in epigraphic tools and services: checklist and analysis

Chairs: Christoph Klose (SMB/MK), Allard Mees (LEIZA)

Members (as of 19.12.2024): Tobias Arera-Rütenik (Univ. Bamberg), Jens Borchert-Pickenhan (SAW/DI), Juliane Eule (SMB/VAM), Matthäus Heil (BBAW/IG), Hannes Kahl (Univ. Trier), Ulrike Peter (BBAW/CN), Christian Prager (Univ. Bonn), Doris Prechel (JGU Mainz), Elisa Roßberger (FU Berlin), Charlotte Schubert (Univ. Leipzig), Domenic Städtler (SPK/IFM), Florian Thiery (LEIZA), Bernhard Weisser (SMB/MK), David Wigg-Wolf (DAI RGK/NOMISMA), Christiane Zimmermann (Univ. Kiel, NAW, Runes-DB)

SC-Decision: 22.11.2024

Designation of Members by the Speaker: 19.12.2024

Bodies Involved: TA 2, TA 4, CC Objects as Information Carriers, CC Bauforschung und Bauhalt, CC Research Software & Engineering, CC Semantic Modelling & Linked Open Data, TWG 3D Annotation, TWG Development of a common NFDI4Objects Objects Ontology (N4O OO) and a Minimal Metadata-Set (N4O MMDS)

External Linking: Univ. Kiel, Bamberg, Bonn, Leipzig, Trier, FU Berlin, JGU Mainz, Textdatenbank und Wörterbuch des Klassischen Maya, NOMISMA, ICOM, Fachgruppe Dokumentation Deutscher Museumsbund e.V., Die AG Minimaldatensatz, SMB VAM

Aims and Objectives

For decades, digital strategies, methods and resources have been developed to make inscriptions as fully and sustainably accessible as possible. The corresponding relational databases, some of which are well established in their communities, focus primarily on providing the textual information of the inscriptions and making them findable and searchable. In recent years, initiatives have also emerged that are working towards the availability of research data in accordance with the FAIR principles and modelling the content of epigraphic databases for the semantic web on the basis of graphs. The material qualities of the inscriptions and the spatial relationship to the carrier object (the written artefact) usually play a subordinate role.

In accordance with the agreed objectives of the CC Objects as information Carriers, the TWG therefore focuses, on a cross disciplinary level, on the status quo of digital epigraphic tools and services with regard to the modelling of the material qualities of the written/inscribed object. The aim is to gain an overview of the potential for researching material qualities in existing digital resources from a user

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perspective. Initially, domain specific and interdisciplinary online databases and resources relevant to inscriptions will be compiled and compared. For this purpose, a checklist will be developed that checks for existing, linked or potentially recordable object attributes. In the course of this, applied and suitable structured thesauri for describing the written objects, in particular their material characteristics, will also be collected. The overview of the tools and services will be used to develop a catalogue of criteria with recommendations for the digital object publication of written artefacts, taking into account how the material properties, in particular the spatial relationships between object and inscription, can be appropriately represented.

Out of Scope

Only digitally available data collections of written artefacts are considered. No new controlled vocabularies or ontologies will be created. However, it will be examined to what extent existing resources are satisfactory in terms of modelling the semantic relationships of the written artefacts, their searchability and reusability, and whether they can be usefully expanded.

Intended Work Results

- 1) Compilation of digital tools and services for the research of written cultural heritage items and categorisation according to 1-5 star criteria and specifications for N4O services.
- 2) Compilation of an overview of relevant structured thesauri/vocabularies for recording object characteristics.
- 3) Preparation of a checklist and examination of the compilation of tools and services on the basis of this.
- 4) Catalogue of criteria for the digital publication of written artefacts with accompanying white paper, which classifies the criteria in the context of research into the material qualities of inscribed/written artefacts and outlines them by way of example. To this end, one or more data set excerpts from best practice examples will also be included as examples.

Envisaged Commons Contributions

White paper on the catalogue of criteria for the object publication of written artefacts with recommendations for data management with regard to the material properties of inscriptions. Possibly (selective) integration of the created overviews into the N4O-Commons-Incubator.

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Abbreviations:

BBAW = Berlin Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften

CC = Community Cluster (NFDI4Objects)

CN = Corpus Nummorum, Berlin

DAI = Deutsches Archäologisches Institut

DI = Deutsche Inschriften

FU = Freie Universität, Berlin

IFM = Institut für Museumsforschung, Berlin

IG = Inscriptiones Graecae

JGU = Johannes-Gutenberg Universität, Mainz

LEIZA = Leibniz Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz

MK = Münzkabinett, Berlin

NAW = Niedersächsische Akademie der Wissenschaften

NOMISMA = Nomisma.org

RGK = Römisch Germanische Kommission, Frankfurt a. Main

SAW = Sächsische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Leipzig

SMB = Staatliche Museen zu Berlin

SPK = Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz

TA2 = Task Area 2: Collecting (NFDI4Objects)

TA4 = Task Area 4: Protecting (NFDI4Objects)

TWG = Temporary Working Group (NFDI4Objects)

Univ. = Universität

VAM = Vorderasiatisches Museum, Berlin